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INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ASTRONOMY TEACHING

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Abstract: This article discusses the improvement of the effectiveness of the use of innovative technologies for the formation of students' knowledge and skills in the educational process.

Key words: pedagogical technology, pedagogical innovation, presentation, innovative, intellectual, didactic.

In recent years, higher educational institutions have been expanding the scope of using modern teaching methods, interactive and innovative technologies in the training of qualified personnel. The use of pedagogical technologies, knowledge, experience and interactive methods on the basis of pedagogical skills in the course of teaching students will lead to deep mastery of subjects and acquire advanced skills.

The concept of innovation is a new economic term that entered our lexicon in the years of independence. Innovative technologies mainly mean introducing innovations and changes to the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers

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and students.

In the course of teaching, innovative technologies can be used in the form of various interactive methods, because each teacher has his own way of teaching. At the stage of quality and efficiency, newly formed modern innovative technologies and pedagogical technologies entered the educational technology. These technologies are being improved, modernized and shaped during each past academic semester. Modern pedagogical technology has its own theory related to the achievements of humanitarian and natural sciences; it is primarily aimed at building the educational process on a scientific basis, and creates a basis for the joint activity of teachers and students based on the wide use of informational means of teaching, didactic materials, and active methods. In the future, as a real engine of educational development, it will have a positive effect on renewing the teacher's activity, building an acceptable (optimal) educational process, and forming the students and young people's open-mindedness, thirst for knowledge, loyalty to the Motherland, and humane feelings. Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative (English) - introduction (dissemination) of newness. Innovation means changes in accordance with the purpose of introducing new, relatively stable (elements) elements to a certain social unit - organization, population, society, group. Currently, there are two views on the process of this innovation change. The first view is that some new idea introduced into life is highlighted, and the second view is the interaction of separately introduced innovations, their primary, competition and, as a result, the replacement of one by the other.

The stages of the innovation process are carried out in the following sequence:

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- it is called the birth of a new idea or the emergence of innovation (discovery stage).
- inventing - the stage of creating something new;
- the stage of practical application of the created innovations;
- the stage of spreading the innovation, its wide application;
- the stage of innovation dominance in a particular field. In pedagogical innovation, the concept of "new" is considered central, and in pedagogical science it arouses interest in specific, conditional, local and subjective innovation.

The concepts of novelty and innovation are different in scientific fields. Innovation is a tool, a new method, methodology, technology, etc. "Innovation" is education; a process that develops according to certain stages. There are 4 main laws of the innovation process, which are interpreted as follows:

1. The law that the environment of pedagogical innovation is not in a vicious circle. In the law of indifference, ideas about the pedagogical process and events are violated, pedagogical awareness is violated, and pedagogical innovation is evaluated. As an example, it is possible to mention "the change of pedagogical consciousness in the process of acceptance of geocentric and heliocentric systems of the world, and the cruel sacrifice was given to realize the truth about the trajectories of the planets.

2. The law of ultimate realization is the vitality of innovation, sooner or later, spontaneously or consciously. For the world system presented above, the geocentric world system, which ruled for several centuries, has consciously given way to the heliocentric system. As a result, a heliocentric system with the sun at its

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center was established.

3. In the law of improvement, pedagogical innovation has a tendency to standardize thinking and practical action.

4. According to the law of periodicity and return of pedagogical innovation, innovation is renewed in new conditions. The interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogic and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that, until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, while in modern technologies, they acquire the knowledge they acquire by themselves. teaches them to search, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions. The pedagogue creates conditions for the development, formation, education and training of the individual in this process, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. In the process of education, the student becomes the main figure.

Such a process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include:

- forcing the student to think independently, create and search, not to be indifferent during the lesson;
- ensure that students have a constant interest in knowledge during the educational process;
- to increase the student's interest in knowledge by independently approaching each issue creatively;
- organization of activities of pedagogue and student in cooperation. Pedagogical

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technologies - in the opinion of teachers, researchers, and practitioners studying the problems of pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technology is only related to information technology, and it is necessary to use it in the teaching process.

The main basis of pedagogical technology is that it depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher and the student to achieve a guaranteed result from the specified goal, that is, every educational technology used in the teaching process, to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal, if the teacher and student can organize a cooperative activity, both will achieve a positive result. if, during the learning process, students can think independently, work creatively, search, analyze, draw their own conclusions, share with each other, group and group, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for such activities, that's it. is the basis of the teaching process. Each lesson, subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a goal-oriented, pre-planned and guaranteed result based on the student's desire.

In order for the teacher to be able to see each lesson as a whole and imagine it, it is necessary to design the future lesson process. In this case, the technological map of the future lesson is drawn up for the teacher based on the nature of the subject, the ability and desire of the students, for each topic, subject taught for each lesson.

Creating such a technological map is not easy, because for this the teacher needs to be aware of pedagogy, psychology, special methods, pedagogical and information technologies, as well as to know a lot of methods and methods. Making each lesson colorful and interesting depends on the planned technological map of the

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lesson, which has been carefully thought out in advance. In order for the lesson to be conducted in the presentation method, slides are prepared based on the given topic. Therefore, when preparing the slides, first of all, it is necessary to take into account the full coverage of the topic, making the pictures and tables clearly visible (not too long) and, most importantly, not tiring the eyes of the students.

It would be appropriate to prepare mechanisms on the topic "Solar system and planets" in multimedia format. If the pictures are given in the form of handouts as much as possible, and the main concepts are explained by the teacher, it will make the students much easier. In the process of teaching, students are treated as individuals, the use of various pedagogical technologies and modern methods enables them to think independently, freely, to research, to approach each issue creatively, to feel responsibility, to conduct scientific research, to analyze, to use scientific literature productively, and most importantly, to read, strengthens their interest in science, pedagogue and his chosen profession. Achieving such a result in practice requires the use of innovative and information technologies in the educational process.

They are very different. We will dwell on some of them and how to conduct them: The "NETWORKS" method is aimed at teaching the student to think logically, to expand the scope of common ideas, to use literature independently.

The "3x4" method is aimed at helping students to think freely, to be able to present various ideas in a wide range, to be able to analyze, draw conclusions, and give definitions during the educational process individually and in small groups.

The "BLIS-GAME" method is aimed at teaching the correct organization of the sequence of actions, logical thinking, and how to choose what is needed from

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many, diverse thoughts and information based on the subject being studied. These modern methods, or technological trainings that help to increase the effectiveness of teaching, help students to form logical, intellectual, creative, critical, independent thinking, develop their abilities, become competitive, mature specialists, and educate professional qualities needed by specialists.

The effective implementation of innovative activity of a teacher depends on a number of conditions. It includes the pedagogue's appropriate communication, his attitude towards opposing opinions, his readiness to express the recognition of a rational situation in various situations. As a result, the pedagogue will have a comprehensive topic that will ensure his knowledge and scientific activity. Self-activation, self-creativity, self-knowledge and creativity motives are important in the work of a pedagogue, which makes it possible to form the creativity of a pedagogue.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above-mentioned considerations:

- in order to increase the efficiency of the educational process, to form solid theoretical knowledge, activities, skills and qualifications of learners, to ensure their transformation into professional skills, the use of new pedagogical technology in the teaching process is being put on the agenda as a requirement of the time and a social necessity.
- the application of new pedagogical technology to the educational process ensures a qualitative change in the content of the general process aimed at personnel training.
- the educational process organized on the basis of using the ideas of the theory of new pedagogical technology leads to a quality indicator of the state of fulfillment

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of the social order regarding the education of a well-rounded person and a qualified specialist.

- the activities of qualified individuals and qualified specialists in the process of social production and their effectiveness lead to the acceleration of social development.
- in each lesson, the teacher prepares interesting questions for the students that match the topic, which is a tool for students to remember the topic.

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